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Cover: graphic reworking of a sheet from Van Dyck's Italian Sketchbook depicting Sofonisba Anguissola

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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Expanding Herstory: Imaging and Imagining Edmonia Lewis' Roman Ateliers

GLORIA JANE BELL
McGill University

Contemplate for a moment this *carte-de-visite*, the only known portrait of artist Edmonia Lewis taken in Rome circa 1876, a decade after she had settled in the city (FIG. 1).¹

Taken at the prestigious Fratelli D'Alessandri Studio, photographers to the Pope, this rare image depicts Lewis at her prime as a sculptor. She projects an aura of confidence and cosmopolitan worldliness, at ease in Rome, the Eternal City.

Described as an “interesting novelty” and a “lady of color” in newspaper accounts, Lewis’s visible difference as an artist of color was remarked upon in global press reports, and she drew upon elements of her Anishinaabe and African American background to emphasize her heritage as distinct from her white American colleagues.² These *carte-de-visites* were used to advertise her aptitude and identity as a sculptor in Rome, and were distributed to potential patrons, critics, and admirers, including Pope Pius IX.³

This essay brings together a diversity of media and imagery to expand and explore Lewis’ place as an artist of international renown in Europe and across the globe. First, this essay conducts an analysis of Lewis’ drawing, *Urania* (1862), before moving on to consider the

¹ This *carte de visite* of Lewis in Rome was discovered by curator Jacqueline Copeland, now in the collection of the Walters Museum of Art.

² “An interesting novelty has sprung up among us, in a city where all our surroundings are of the olden time. Miss Edmonia Lewis, a lady of color, has taken a studio in Rome and works as a sculptress.” Monday March 5, 1866, *Sheffield Independent*.

Some key texts on Lewis include Charmaine Nelson, *The Color of Stone: Sculpting the Black Female Subject in Nineteenth-century America* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2007); Kirsten Buick, *Child of the Fire: Mary Edmonia Lewis and the Problem of Art History’s Black and Indian Subject* (Duke University Press, London: 2010); Kirsten Buick, “The Ideal Works of Edmonia Lewis: Invoking and Inverting Biography,” *American Art* 9, no. 2 (1995): 4–22.

³ Lewis received a Papal blessing for her work. *Notable American Women, 1607-1950: A Biographical Dictionary*, Volume 3, By Edward T. James, Janet Wilson James, Paul S. Boyer, Radcliffe College, 398.

locations of Lewis' artist studios and some possible inspirations in order to create a new archive and add to the complexity of her oeuvre. This analysis will add new understandings of American women artists in Rome, and Black and Indigenous artists and their lived experiences thereby expanding the canon of art history and archival studies. I aim to create new ways of thinking about Lewis as an artist of global renown amongst an international group of sculptors in nineteenth century Rome such as Harriet Hosmer, Thomas Crawford, and Anne Whitney, as well as writers including Henry Longfellow and advocates including Frederick Douglass. The essay also incorporates some of my experiences in Rome as a fellow expatriate like Lewis. I seek to expand the form of the essay as a tool for mapping out a new type of history and herstory as well as a method of writing about art and expanding the mapping of Indigenous experiences into new imaginative spaces. The media herein are a form of worldbuilding, blowing off the dust of the Euro-canon and expanding our understandings of Indigenous and Black artists abroad, thereby "decentering the United States."⁴

The Goddess Urania: Lewis' Muse

The only extant drawing from Lewis' early career is of the mythological Greek FIG. *Urania* (1862), a muse of astronomers and goddess of the arts (FIG. 2). Lewis completed this drawing while in Boston at Oberlin College, where she was garnering support for her eventual trip to Rome while working on medallions depicting Abolitionist Civil War military men such as Colonel Robert Gould Shaw. The *Urania* drawing demonstrates how Lewis worked through artistic problems of shadow and light, while refining her skills in depicting a shapely female form which she would later work out in sculpture with works such as *Minnehaha* (1868) and *Cleopatra* (1876). In *Urania*, the goddess is cloaked in a loose gown and casts her eyes onto the compass and globe. These instruments of astronomy also foreshadow Lewis' own future travels as an artist. She travelled globally, back and forth across the Atlantic, and perhaps saw some elements of herself in this goddess and her prophetic abilities to see into the future. Urania was also associated with Christian poetry, and perhaps Lewis, having converted to Catholicism from Protestantism, also appreciated this aspect of the muse. The drawing showcases Lewis' interest and talent in depicting Neoclassical subjects such as Greek and Roman goddesses associated with 18th and 19th century innovations in art, archaeology, architecture, music, literature and decorative arts.

⁴ Shannon Ketchum, "Native American Cosmopolitan Modernisms," *Third Text*, 19: 4 (2005): 361.

It was made by candlelight suggested by the wax present on the drawing; an interesting method that parallels sculptural techniques and ways of viewing, as sculptors were encouraged to view three-dimensional artworks in the round and by candlelight in order to appreciate their full effect. One of her first commissions, Lewis produced this drawing for a classmate named Clara Steele Norton as a wedding gift in 1862.⁵

No drawings are known from Lewis' years abroad in Italy, France and the UK, and her sculptural works are still being discovered after years of neglect and misattribution. This speaks to the ways in which art history has neglected artists of color by relying on the faulty documentation methods of nineteenth century record keeping, namely colonial biases towards artists of color and Indigenous artists whose names were often left unrecorded alongside other pertinent details. The scholarship on Lewis, like many artists of color and Indigenous artists, has been scarce in previous centuries but today continues to grow. Perhaps as time goes by, more of Lewis' works including drawings and sketches will be revealed as public interest and awareness in her artistic career expands. The most recent inclusion of Lewis' sculpture, *The Old Arrowmaker* (1872), in the groundbreaking Native American Arts exhibition *Hearts of Our People* (2019) serves as one such example of the growing interest in Lewis as an artist of international renown and talent. In addition, her inclusion in such exhibitions works towards unsettling dated ideas regarding art history and Indigenous artists.⁶

On Methods: What inspires this project?

This essay aims to write art histories that honor Indigenous artists and artists of color. I first came across Lewis while conducting research on Indigenous artists in Rome and thinking about the longer trajectory and experience of Indigenous artists abroad and within the Eternal City. I had been undertaking this research in archives in Rome such as the Jesuit Archive (ARSI), the Propaganda Fide Archive and Library, the Vatican Secret Archives and the Vatican Apostolica Archive in relation to exhibitions at the Vatican. Throughout the exploration of these archives and as I read through thousands of pages of missionary correspondence, I was thinking about how we can trace the experiences of Indigenous artisans and artists by utilizing archival records. For many artists of color and Indigenous

⁵ "Drawing After Urania," Oberlin College Archives, accessed August 25, 2021, <http://dcollections.oberlin.edu/cdm/ref/collection/objects/id/668>

⁶ "Hearts of Our People: Native Women Artists," Smithsonian American Art Museum, accessed August 26, 2021, <https://americanart.si.edu/exhibitions/native-women-artists#>

artists, the archive always remains incomplete. This is due to its colonial nature as a host for the biases of missionaries who solely recorded their version of history and what mattered to them. I was and still am thinking expansively of Indigenous artists' experiences abroad, and when I found out about Lewis living in Rome, defying the odds for Indigenous artists in the nineteenth century and being recognized for her sculptural work in an international and competitive circle, I felt incredibly inspired. Lewis' tenacity and audacity as an artist of Anishinaabe ascent from the Mississauga of the New Credit First Nation on her mother's side (or Chippewa), and Haitian on her father's side, continue to inspire my work thinking broadly about the experiences of Indigenous and Black artists working in the art world. I also use the term Indigenous to build solidarity and awareness around Indigenous movements for self-determination and sovereignty today across Turtle Island (a term Indigenous nations used to refer to Canada and the USA) and the global move for Indigenous sovereignty and decolonization of mind, body, spirit.⁷ Most records I had scanned through barely mention Indigenous artists from the Americas. On the rare occasions that they are mentioned, they are not properly named, and their work is often listed as "primitive" rather than recognized because of its merit or achievements; such derogatory interpretations continue to this day. Thus, this essay is partly in support and in

⁷ On the experiences of Indigenous travelers abroad see the work of Carl Benn, *Mohawks on the Nile: Natives Among the Canadian Voyageurs in Egypt, 1884-1885* (Toronto: Dundurn Press, 2009); John Brown Childs and Guillermo Delgado, *Indigeneity: Collected Essays* (Santa Cruz, CA: New Pacific Press, 2012); Karsten Fitz, *Visual Representations of Native Americans: Transnational Contexts and Perspectives* (Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2012); Kate Flint, *The Transatlantic Indian, 1776-1930* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2009); Shari M Huhndorf, *Going Native: Indians in the American Cultural Imagination* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2001); Shari M. Huhndorf, *Mapping the Americas: the Transnational Politics of Contemporary Native Culture* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2009); Terry Goldie, *Fear and Temptation: The Image of the Indigene in Canadian, Australian, and New Zealand Literatures* (Montreal: McGill-Queen's, 2014); Jace Weaver, *The Red Atlantic: American Indigenes and the Making of the Modern World, 1000-1927* (Chapel Hill: UNC Press, 2014). See also Steve Friesen and Chladiuk François, *Lakota Performers in Europe: Their Culture and the Artifacts They Left Behind*, (Norman, OK: University of Oklahoma Press, 2017); Emily L Voelker, "Unfixing the Frame: Visualizing Histories of Transcultural Contact, Exchange & Performance in Prince Roland Bonaparte's Peaux-Rouges (1884)". *Transatlantica*. (2) (2017); Emily Burns, *Transnational Frontiers: The American West in France*, (Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 2018); Dagmar Wernitznig, *Europe's Indians, Indians in Europe: European Perceptions and Appropriations of Native American Cultures from Pocahontas to the Present*, (Lanham: University Press of America, 2007); Christian F Feest, *Indians and Europe: An Interdisciplinary Collection of Essays*, (Aachen: Rader Verlag, 1987).

remembrance of all these artists who were never named, or who were misrepresented and underappreciated. Walking through Rome today, encountering Lewis' studios and other traces of the artist, continues to inspire my scholarly journey and research process. Finding out about Edmonia Lewis' life in Rome, really changed my project, as it provided an example where Indigenous artists were not just anonymous artists unknown forever in the Vatican archives. Although Indigenous people are often subsumed within the historical colonial archive, Lewis remains a strong example of a prolific artist who continued to defy the odds throughout her life.

On the Ground Research: Tracing Lewis' Studios

The very studio where Lewis' had her previously mentioned portrait taken, the Fratelli D'Alessandri studio at via del Corso No 12, was not far from the Canova studio at Via della Frezza 27 where the artist first settled after arriving in Rome.⁸ The Fratelli D'Alessandri photographers mainly took portraits of dignitaries including cardinals, the Pope, Roman nobility, and other important figures in Roman society, and Lewis added herself to this list as an artist of international renown building cultural capital with the latest in photographic technology and scientific advances. Lewis was a celebrity at the time. Her *carte-de-visite* is sepia-toned, a popular choice in the studio, and most likely an albumen print from collodion on glass negatives.⁹ These *carte-de-visite* were made in the millions and distributed and collected across the world.¹⁰ Here we have illustrated the "apparatus equipped with four lenses for the *carte-de-visite*," the same technology used for Lewis' image (FIG. 3).

It is interesting to also note that Lewis had a series of photographs made in Chicago at the famous studio of Henry Rocher (1870) (FIG. 4).¹¹ The Roman photograph differs significantly from the Chicago photos, in that Lewis poses for a full-length portrait, in comparison to the more cropped images of her taken at Rocher's studio. The posing of the Roman photo projects a more confident demeanor overall, as Lewis stands with her arms

⁸ On Italian interest in Native Americans see Fedora Giordano, "The Anxiety of Discovery: The Italian Interest in Native American Studies," *Rivista di Studi Americani*, 5 (1994): 81–109.

⁹ Piero Becchetti, *Fotografi e Fotografia in Italia, 1839-1880*, (Roma: Edizioni Quasar, 1978), 45.

¹⁰ Gordon Baldwin and Martin Jurgens, *Looking at Photographs: A Guide to Technical Terms*, (Los Angeles: Getty Museum, 2009), 14.

¹¹ "Edmonia Lewis," Harvard Art Museums, accessed August 25, 2021, From the Harvard Art Museums' collections Edmonia Lewis (1845-1907)

crossed over her chest in a power pose. The Chicago *carte-de-visite* also feature the bohemian wear that Lewis' was known for including a jacket with fringe and billowing clothes. The ring on her left hand suggests she was married and or was a very devout Catholic and wanted to project an image of genteel cosmopolitanism. She was not afraid to stand out. In the Anglo-community of American artists, her Catholic devotion would have made her singular. In the background, Lewis' elbow rests near a Greek meander, a symbol used throughout neoclassical artworks to celebrate the eternal nature of life. The fact that Lewis had her portraits made in Chicago and Rome illustrates her renown as an artist and her established cultural capital. She used photography as a medium for self-promotion as well as building a picture world and a world of pictures against the destruction of Indigenous and Black lifeways. Perhaps not inadvertently, she created an archive of photographs and sculpture that celebrated Black and Indigenous achievements. The legacy of her oeuvre creates another space of imagining and imaging against the annihilation of Indigenous and Black life during the period of the Civil War and genocidal programs of Indian removal across Turtle Island.

Thus, her artworks and life experience worked against the double-edged sword of neoclassicism. For Indigenous artists, this style was fraught with complicity in that neoclassical art, prominent on governmental buildings throughout the U.S., promoted the destruction and demise of Indigenous peoples and lifeways across Turtle Island. Lewis' life as an Anishinaabe artist complicates the conventional narratives often told of neoclassical artists at the time, while her artworks interrupted the American vision of Indigenous peoples as doomed to live and die on colonial reservations, as she defied all odds and achieved celebrity status in Rome.¹²

The Artist Studios as Indigenous Spaces

Part of my broader project is to map out Lewis' studios in relation to other artists of her time and hopefully eventually add other women artists as well as other Black and Indigenous artists, sculptors, patrons and relevant FIG.s in her network. I am thinking of the using the term 'mapping' in a broadly creative sense, aware of the ways mapping has been used as a colonial tool to negate and control Indigenous and Black lives. As art

¹² This subject is not the topic of this essay but deserves a footnote here. Many artists such as Thomas Crawford, Ferdinand Pettrich and others promoted the death of Indigenous (Native American) subjects in their artworks. See for example, Thomas Crawford, *Mexican Girl Dying*, 1848, accessed August 25, 2021, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/10575>.

historians Ruth Phillips and Elizabeth Harney note, “Decolonizing critiques employing mapping – or remapping – to acknowledge the centrality of place in the crafting of modernist Indigenous subjectivities. Such maps can complicate accepted and expected axes of colonial-modern movement between center and periphery by allowing us to recognize complex local, regional, and global sources of artistic production and consumption, networks of travel, and polycentric nodes of modernist creation.”¹³ This essay seeks to create another form of mapping which upends the axes of expectation around Lewis’s life and works, invoking new ways of understanding her studios and even physically tracing some of the routes she travelled between her studios. Lewis, the “colored genius at Rome,” had a complex life as a traveler, creating new axes and nodes across the Atlantic through countries, states, and Indigenous territories.¹⁴ Lewis was a nomad and traveler like her mother’s people, the Anishinaabe, and although she never returned to her traditional territories, in some ways she completed the circle of her maternal ancestry in that she continued a nomadic life, albeit in different geographies.

Nomadic Visions: Edmonia in Rome and Pompei

*There was some magic about me. I knew it from the way others responded, had always responded to me, as if I were larger than life. Then there are all the stories told about me, some false, most of them true.*¹⁵

Like photography theorist Susan Sontag’s investigation into the charmed world of historic Napoli and erupting Mount Vesuvius, part of my current research revolves around

¹³ Elizabeth Harney and Ruth B Phillips, eds. *Mapping Modernisms: Art, Indigeneity, Colonialism*, (Durham: Duke University Press, 2018), 9.

¹⁴ “The Colored Genius at Rome,” *The Christian Recorder*, March 31, 1866. On the history of the Ojibwe and the Mississauga New Credit First Nation, see Heidi Bohaker, “Reading Anishinaabe Identities: Meaning and Metaphor in Nindoodem Pictographs,” *Ethnohistory* 57, no. 1 (2010): 11–33; Melissa Nelson, “The Hydromythology of the Anishinaabeg,” *Centering Anishinaabeg Studies: Understanding the World through Stories* (Troy: Michigan State University Press, 2013), 213–33; Donald B Smith, *Mississauga Portraits: Ojibwe Voices from Nineteenth-century Canada* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2013); Robert Penner, “The Ojibwe Renaissance: Transnational Evangelicalism and the Making of an Algonquian Intelligentsia, 1812–1867,” *American Review of Canadian Studies* 45, no. 1 (2015): 71–92.

¹⁵ Susan Sontag, *The Volcano Lover: A Romance*, (New York: Farrar: 1992), 404.

thinking about what might have inspired Lewis including ancient sites, natural sciences, and esoteric endeavors (FIG. 5). I am interested in whether Lewis investigated scientific discoveries of the time. We can imagine that she travelled to Naples and even further south, to see the then recently discovered ancient city of Pompei. The city of Pompei would have been a major inspiration for a neoclassical sculptor interested in drawing on ancient Roman sites but reinterpreting them for a nineteenth century audience and aesthetic.

As in *The Volcano Lover*, much magic and mystery surrounds Lewis' life and experiences, and her works also remain to be discovered. While there might be some fiction in the stories told about Lewis, there also remains much truth. The larger scholarship on Lewis continues to grow, and there are more stories being told. I hope my article adds to the stories told regarding Lewis, as a gesture which seeks to expand appreciation of Lewis' work, life story, and her ateliers, as well as complicating existing narratives. In a related vein, Ruth Phillips and Elizabeth Harney have written that "we are not interested in producing a global art history that simply replaces one normative story with another. Rather we write in opposition, both to an established canon and to the universalizing tendencies that are resurfacing in world art studies."¹⁶

Similarly, this essay does not work to oppose the discipline of world art studies but rather seeks to add another layer of complexity to scholarship on Lewis' position within these discourses. Lewis spent time in major urban centres such as Florence, Paris, London, and Chicago, where she worked to expand public awareness of her artworks and commissions as well as exhibiting in major colonial centers and fairs such as the 1876 Centennial Exposition in Philadelphia.

Lewis, like many Indigenous travelers before and after her time, was a cosmopolitan, defying boundaries of what Indigenous artists could do and challenging global perceptions along the way. Theorist Shannon Ketchum has also noted the power of Native American artists in actively refining and refracting staid notions of art and culture. She writes that, "The anti-colonial struggle that modernity entreats has always been exercised by Native Americans across time and space or, in short, in history. As a political force to be reckoned with on local, state and federal levels, Native Americans have redefined modernity all along as a means of empowering their journey to freedom and self-determination."¹⁷ Lewis' life

¹⁶ Harney and Phillips, 3.

¹⁷ Ketchum, 359.

story and artworks continue to inspire artists and art historians today in their efforts to de-center the western canon.

Like Lewis, I travelled across the Atlantic many times to conduct research in Rome, often thinking about Lewis' similar experiences as an expatriate. I remember sitting in Rome talking with a close Roman friend; we were sitting near the Church which held the frescoes of St Ignacius of Loyala, the first Jesuit to travel to the Americas and attempt to proselytize First Nations. It was October and the air was still warm. We sat in the shadows and leaned against the cool marble. I remember telling my friend about Lewis, about her audacity and her work in the city. We walked around to some of her studios and talked about what she might have felt or seen in nineteenth century Rome, pursuing a life as an unchaperoned international artist and dressing in the bohemian style wearing a beret, shawl and long free-fitting dress. We also spoke about Indigenous presences and places in the city, imagining what they might be like, as well as discussing curating Indigenous art at the Venice Biennale.¹⁸ Walking around, looking for her studios I felt a sense of hope in Lewis' tenacity and ability to become a professional artist, defying odds and creating a successful life and novel framework for herself in the Eternal City.

Finding Lewis' Studios

We walked to her first studio, the original studio of Antonio Canova at Via della Frezza 27. Looking from the outside there are ancient putti, busts, and Roman fragments on the walls, suitable for neoclassical artists obsessed with studying the ancient past. The windows are high and large, perfect for a sculptor as they allow light to stream in and illuminate the entire room. Lewis placed herself on a continuum of neoclassical artists and created a new vision for herself and her patrons with works that represented and celebrated Indigenous and Black subjects, unprecedented amongst her peers. John Murray's *Handbook of Rome and its Environs* (1867) has this to note on visitors to artists' studios, "Among the characteristics of Modern Rome capable of affording high interest to the intellectual visitor, there are few that offer a greater charm than the artists' studios. Travelers in general are little aware of the interest which they are calculated to afford, and many leave Rome

¹⁸ "Radical Curating: Venice Biennale," Nancy Mithlo Venice Biennale, accessed August 25, 2021, https://nancymariemithlo.com/Radical_Curating_Indigenous_Art_at_the_Venice_Biennale/index.html

without making the acquaintance of a single artist”¹⁹ The handbook then mentions Lewis as “Miss Lewis (American) Via Della Frezza 27,” and lists her address at the former studio of Italian Antonio Canova (FIG. 6 and 7), a notable and celebrated Roman artist. The studio is a few minutes walk from the bustling Piazza di Spagna and the intellectual and artistic hub of Café Greco, frequented by writers and artists. Lewis took up at this studio when she first moved to Rome, surely drawing inspiration from the larger-than-life Papal FIG.s, mythical goddesses and Roman centurions created by Canova and left as models in the studio.

During 1867, she moved into a studio on Via Gregoriana, alongside artists such as Anne Whitney, Cushman and Hosmer. She worked on her statues exploring themes of freedom for Black communities and Indigenous nations including *Forever Free* (1867) and *Marriage of Hiawatha* (1868). Pennsylvanian businessman Alfred Huidekoper noted in his *Glimpses of Europe*, on meeting Lewis, “she evidently has artistic aims; spoke of her desire to catch the more spirited effects of a first impression, rather to embody in the clay the harder likeness that comes to one as the features grow more tame by familiarity. She has in her studio several renderings of Indian subjects, 'Hiawatha's Wooing and Wedding,' 'Indians Wrestling,'" making note of Lewis’ works in progress and her “fair ability.”²⁰ Lewis, a professional artist impressed businessman like Huidekoper with her skill and tact and attracted commissions throughout her career.

The studio was also close to the Spanish steps which we can see here in (FIG. 8).²¹ Lewis would have been very familiar with this scene as she climbed the steps to Via Gregoriana, where the studios of Harriet Hosmer and her other contemporary sculptors lived. It was about a ten minute walk from Antonio Canova’s former studio up the stairs to visit her colleague Hosmer, the American sculptor famous for the work *Zenobia in Chains* (exhibited at the Great London Exposition) in 1862 and on view in Boston where Lewis was part of the Abolitionist community.²² Harriet Hosmer’s studio on Via Gregoriana can

¹⁹ “John Murray’s Handbook of Rome,” 1867, accessed August 25, 2021, <https://archive.org/stream/ahandbookromean07firgoog#page/n50/mode/1up>

²⁰ Alfred Huidekoper, *Glimpses of Europe in 1851 and 1867-8*, (Meadville, Pa.: Printed for the Author, 1882) 184.

²¹ “Trinità dei Monti,” Roma Sparita, accessed August 25, 2021, <https://www.romasparita.eu/foto-roma-sparita/54765/trinita-dei-monti-28>

²² Melissa Dabakis: *A Sisterhood of Sculptors: American Artists in Nineteenth-Century Rome*, (Pennsylvania: Penn State University Press, 2014), 150.

still be found today, its door adorned with the face of Medusa, a suitable muse for an independent sculptor.

Perhaps she even attended services at the church of Trinità dei Monti, perched above the Piazza di Spagna, with her best friend and sculptress Lady Isobel Cholmondeley, who also attended Lewis' Catholic confirmation.²³ The street around the studio spot is narrow but the morning light hits it in interesting ways, a beautiful and inspiring spot for an artist of stature. This area around Piazza di Spagna is home to the studios of fellow women sculptors, and close to contemporaries such as Ferdinand Pettrich's studio.

A few years later, she moved to via San Nicola di Tolentino, number 7, an area of Rome halfway between Piazza Barberini and Piazza di San Bernardo and about a ten-minute walk from Termini train station (FIG. 9, 10, 11). Located in the Piazza Barberini, the *Triton Fountain* sits in the main square. Made by Baroque artist Bernini, the striking work commands presence. Lewis likely bought her fruit and vegetables at the fresh market stands that used to surround the fountain. The streets are lined with orange trees that bloom in the spring and the fall. Lewis was listed again in Murray's *Handbook of Rome*, evidence of her success as a sculptor in an international competitive economic sphere and the ongoing importance of her work and her busy life fulfilling commissions from American, British, and European patrons and admirers. Visiting her at this studio and seeing work in progress for the impressive statue of *Hagar* (1875), Women's rights and emancipation activist Frances Williard made this note in her journal on January 4, 1870,

Edmonia Lewis, "the 'colored' lady from Boston has a pretty little studio very pleasantly located on our street, & her work as well as her manners are very pleasing. I took especial pleasure in my visit, because, it is particularly agreeable to see one who, like her, occupies an exceptional & not a desirable position in the world's estimate, gifted with the power to create beauty & harmony for itself--blessed with that sweetest of all solaces--an engrossing & congenial occupation ... She has a full-size statue of Hagar in the moment of her despair--her most ambitious work, & one full of promise for her mature fame ... A privilege this of

²³ "Marilyn Richardson Correspondence," Excerpt from a letter written to Jacquelyn Lewis-Harris, Assistant Curator at the saint lewis art museum, from Marilyn Richardson, January 23, 1997. On the bust of Lewis created by Lady Isobel Cholmondeley see Susan Crowe, "Visual Narratives and the Portrait Busts of Edmonia Lewis," MA Thesis, University of Missouri-Kansas City, 2010.

her genius to which many a wealthy traveler vainly aspires ... I took "solid comfort" in the contemplation of this girl, so free, so worthily at work, so thoroughly appreciated for what she has done & will do. An anomaly it is indeed, to find at Rome--the most conservative, most middle-age city of Europe--the daughter of a proscribed race leading a true & perfectly untrammelled life-- ... going her way quietly free as air--just as one day all men & women are to be.²⁴

Lewis was admired by both American visitors and Italian notables building an indelible trace throughout her life in Rome, travelling and working on both sides of the Atlantic to fulfill commissions, large sculptural works and busts. Her artworks, life example and studio were an important meeting point and intellectual hub for supporters and admirers and continued to be an essential stop during visits to Rome. Abolitionist, statesman, orator and media mogul Frederick Douglass visited in the 1880s when he was staying with African American Sarah Parker Remond at her home Palazzo Maroni, the nurse activist active in Florence and Rome.²⁵ He writes about Lewis' talent with a chisel and marble, "Miss Lewis is young, has ability, and what is sometimes worth more, independence and a wonderful amount of courage."²⁶ Perhaps it was also at this moment that Douglass chose to have his face immortalized in marble. Lewis was thus part of an intellectual elite in the Eternal City and at this point had been working on her last major commission the *Adoration of the Magi* (1883).²⁷ This marble bas relief was commissioned for the Chapel of St. Mary the Virgin, Orchard Street, Baltimore. While I attempted to find the exact location of her studio, it is highly likely that her original studio was demolished. Pictured here are the photographs from where Lewis' last known studio existed in Rome. Coming full circle back to the Roman *carte-de-visite*, it is probable that Lewis travelled to see the marble bas-relief installed in Baltimore and left her Roman *carte-de-visite* there as a type of calling card, as it was discovered at an antique shop by the curator Jacqueline Copeland in the city more than one hundred years later.

²⁴ Sirpa A Salenius, "US-American new women in Italy 1853-1870," *Comparative Literature and Culture* 14, no. 1 (2012): 328-329.

²⁵ On Remond's experiences see Sirpa A Salenius, "Negra d'America Remond and Her Journeys," *Comparative Literature and Culture* 14.5 (2012): <<https://doi.org/10.7771/1481-4374.2156>>.

²⁶ Frederick Douglass, "Miss Edmonia Lewis," *New National Era*, September 25, 1873.

²⁷ A photo is available of the bas relief here *The Adoration of the Magi* (edmonialewis.com), accessed August 26, 2021.

Vatican Collections and the Apollo Belvedere

In addition to her community of expat artists and the Arcadian Academy that celebrated female genius and talent, Lewis drew inspiration from across Rome (FIG. 12).²⁸ The Vatican collections of ancient Roman statuary and Egyptian art likely deeply influenced her sculptural busts and cupids. In particular, the Vatican Lapidary Collection has a hall of ancient marble busts and putti that surely inspired her work. In particular, the Vatican Lapidary Collection has a hall of ancient marble busts and putti that surely inspired her work. Another important sculpture to influence neoclassical American sculptors was the Apollo Belvedere.

American artist Benjamin West made this remark upon seeing the Roman god Apollo Belvedere within the Vatican collections, ‘My God, how like it is to a young Mohawk warrior!’²⁹ The equation between classical Roman antiquity and the Native American hero was reproduced by many American artists in the following century. Like ancient Roman warriors, Native Americans were equated with a noble, heroic past, and Lewis’ contemporaries created many sculptures following this theme which depicting dying and heroic FIG.s such as *The Dying Tecumseh* (1856) by Ferdinand Pettrich. Lewis, an astute FIG., was likely aware of this equation and perhaps even saw the chiseled sculpture of the Roman god at the Vatican herself. She may have even viewed it by candlelight in the evening hours, as was the contemporary trend in viewing sculptures in the round.

Indigenous Futures: Indigenous and Black Artists Working in Rome

More broadly, Lewis is part of a legacy and history of Indigenous artists working and living in Rome. Other artists of color working in Rome in the period are not known at this point but there were certainly African American collectors such as the couple Antoinette Rutgers Thomas and James Thomas, who commissioned Lewis to complete their portrait busts.³⁰ More recently, the Cherokee artist Kay Walking Stick completed archival research and reflections while staying in Rome and conducting research at the Vatican collections

²⁸ On the Arcadian Academy see Dabakis, 27.

²⁹ John Galt, *The Life of Benjamin West* ed. by Nathalia Wright, (Gainesville, Florida: Scholars’ Facsimiles & Reprints, 1960). See also Jules David Prown, *Art as Evidence: Writings on Art and Material Culture*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2001), 99.

³⁰ Susan Crowe, “Visual Narratives and the Portrait Busts of Edmonia Lewis,” MA Thesis, University of Missouri-Kansas City, 2010.

in 1998. Walking Stick produced a journal of watercolors which reference the Aztec Codex and reinterpret it using a Native American vision.³¹

Thus Lewis forms part of a continuum of Indigenous artists and Black artists working and travelling and living *la dolce vita* in Rome, despite colonial efforts at the time to keep artists of color from receiving proper recognition or appreciation of their talents. Perhaps Lewis also drew inspiration from the sculpture of a Black Roman diplomat at the Basilica di Santa Maria Maggiore.³² More broadly in Rome and at the Vatican, Indigenous rights and recognition are an ongoing matter of sovereignty and diplomacy. Is there a magic or a deep time or a deep place and space of reckoning in the rediscovery of Lewis' works?

To close this essay, let us look at the painting by Cherokee Nation artist America Meredith, *Portrait of Edmonia Lewis* (2007) (FIG. 13). A sumptuous red cloak surrounds the artist's shoulders, she holds her right hand out, offering up a world of varying interpretations to her viewer. She has a slight smile and a knowing look, confident in her abilities as a sculptor of international reknown. Her green cravat tied around her neck and the red cloak contrast nicely, ascribing her a bohemian style suitable for her life as an expatriate artist and celebrity. The text in gold "Edmonia Lewis Missisauga Ojibwe Sculptor 1844-1911," functions almost as a sort of memorial or epitaph. But Lewis' expression draw us to further consider her life and work and think about her ongoing relevancy for artists and art historians today. The portrait pays an homage to the Renaissance portraits of the Popes by Titian, Diego Velázquez, and Raphael. The sumptuous velvet of her cloak also recalls the red ermine-lined cloaks of the Papacy, but in this case also functions as a homage to her Anishinaabe ancestry. The power of red and of ancient Rome is carried forth in this image with this portrait of a woman who defied the odds to create new picture worlds for Indigenous and Black artists.

³¹ "Kay Walking Stick," accessed August 26, 2021, <http://kaywalkingstick.com/>

³² W.E.B. Du Bois Institute for African and African American Research, and Menil Collection (Houston, Tex.). *The Image of the Black in Western Art*. Edited by David Bindman, Henry Louis Gates, and Karen C. C Dalton. Newed. *Image of the Black in Western Art*, (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2010).

APPENDIX

FIG. 1, Fratelli D'Alessandri, Rome, Carte de visite of Edmonia Lewis, ca. 1874-76. Albumen silver print, Walters Art Museum Collection

FIG. 2, Edmonia Lewis, Urania, 1862, drawing, Oberlin College Archives

*Apparecchio munito di quattro obiettivi
per « carte de visite ».*

FIG. 3, Unknown artist, Apparatus for carte-de-visite, Source: Piero Becchetti, *Fotografi e Fotografia in Italia, 1839-1880*, (Roma: Edizioni Quasar, 1978), 45.

FIG. 4, Henry Rocher, Portrait of Edmonia Lewis, 1870, albumen silver print, Harvard Art Museums/Fogg Museum, Transfer from Special Collections, Fine Arts Library, Harvard College Library, Bequest of Evert Jansen Wendel

FIG. 5, Jasmine Wells, Scenes from Edmonia Lewis' Life, Seen: Edmonia Lewis, BOOM! 2020

FIG. 6, Photograph by Author, Via della Frezza 27, Roma

FIG. 7, Photograph by Author

FIG. 8, Unknown Photographer, Scalinata di Trinità dei Monti, 1860, Roma dalla Belle Epoque al Regime Gemika International

FIG. 9, Photograph by Author, Location near Edmonia Lewis' last known studio, Roma

FIG. 10, Photograph by Author, Location near Edmonia Lewis' last known studio, Roma

FIG. 11, Photograph by Author, Location near Edmonia Lewis' last known studio, Roma

FIG. 12, Photograph by Author, Vatican Lapidary Collection

FIG. 13, America Meredith, Portrait of Edmonia Lewis, 2007, Courtesy of the artist, Private Collection